

Screening for blast (Bl) resistance in Hangzhou, China

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Rice Bl is one of the most widely distributed diseases in China. Heavy infections on panicles are often detrimental to rice yields. We screened 113 entries under natural disease pressure at the CNRRI Fuyang Experiment Station during 1987.

One-month-old seedlings were transplanted in 2 rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing. One row each of susceptible checks Yuan Feng Zao and Guang Lu Ai No. 4 and resistant check Er Jiu Feng were transplanted between each entry and on all sides. Soil was sandy loam with medium fertility. Fertilizer was applied at 75-37.5-25 kg NPK/ha. A local predominant strain of the Bl pathogen was collected and isolated from naturally infected leaves and a

Varieties or lines resistant to Bl at CNRRI, Fuyang Experiment Station, Hangzhou, China, 1987.

Variety or line	Score ^a		
	Seedling	Leaf	Neck
BG380-2	5	0	1
C712035	4	1	0
C721313	3	1	0
C731110	3	1	0
HPU5010-PLP21-2-1B	4	0	0
IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2	4	0	0
IR19349-135-2-3-2-1	3	0	0
IR19670-57-1-1-3	3	1	3
IR31868-64-2-3-3-3	4	0	0
IR32429-122-3-1-2	4	0	0
IR35353-94-2-1-3	3	0	0
IR35410-16-3-2-2-2-2	3	3	0
IR37865-29-3-1-3	4	0	0
IR39379-20-1-2-1-1	2	0	0
IR7732-RGA-B-A96-1	4	2	0
SR9713-31-2-3	0	0	0
Suakoko 8 (2526)	3	1	3
Tetep	3	3	0
32-Xuan-5-B	4	0	3
Er Jiu Feng (resistant check)	5	2	5
Guang Lu Ai No. 4 (susceptible check)	9	5	9

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale.

spore suspension sprayed at 2 wk after transplanting to help initiate infection. The spore suspension concentration was adjusted to 5×10^5 /ml. Seedling, leaf, and neck Bl were scored at four leaf ages, maximum tillering, and maturity.

Of 113 entries screened, 19 were

resistant to Bl (see table). C721313, C731110, HPU5010-PLP21-2-1B, IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2, IR31868-64-2-3-3-3, IR32429-122-3-1-2, IR39379-20-1-2-1-1, IR7732-RGA-B-A96-1 have good grain quality and high yield potential. □

Background resistance to bacterial blight (BB) hill and leaf infection

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In the Philippines, rices with the *Xa-4* gene for resistance to race 1 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* are affected by the virulence of race 2, the dominant bacterial pathogen population. Although more than 80% of the rice area is planted to varieties with such resistance, BB occurs endemically in specific localities. The level of infection varies, even though the same resistance gene *Xa-4* confers resistance.

We assessed reactions of commonly planted varieties to both virulent and avirulent races to determine if other components influence their resistance. Races 1 and 2 and IR20, IR22, IR26, IR36, IR42, IR48, IR50, IR54, IR56, IR58, IR60, and IR62 (all known to carry *Xa-4*) were used.

Plants raised in the screenhouse were inoculated at 21 d after sowing with isolate PXO 61 of race 1 (avirulent) and PXO 86 of race 2 (virulent). IR24, which carries no gene for BB resistance, was the susceptible check. Hill and leaf/ hill infection was measured at three growth stages.

The relative resistance index (RI) used

Resistance or susceptibility of IR cultivars carrying *Xa-4* gene for BB resistance to 2 races of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* at 3 growth stages. ^a IRRI, 1986 dry season.

Variety	Early tillering		Maximum tillering		Booting stage	
	Hill infection (%)	Leaf infection (%)	Hill infection (%)	Leaf infection (%)	Hill infection (%)	Leaf infection (%)
<i>PXO 61</i>						
IR24 ^b	91.6	29.6	91.6	23.8	52.0	14.8
IR56	91.6	28.4	87.4	17.0	52.0	9.6
IR50	45.8	11.4	50.0	5.4	8.2	0.8
IR60	43.8	11.8	33.4	3.2	4.2	0.2
IR42	37.6	11.2	6.2	0.2	—	—
IR22	33.4	7.2	12.4	1.8	—	—
IR58	33.4	6.8	18.8	1.8	4.2	0.6
IR62	27.0	7.4	29.2	3.8	10.4	2.2
IR36	27.0	9.6	20.8	1.6	—	0
IR20	25.0	7.6	12.4	1.6	14.6	1.8
IR54	20.8	5.6	35.4	2.2	2.2	0
IR26	18.8	3.8	6.2	0.6	2.0	0.4
<i>PXO 86</i>						
IR24 ^b	73.0	23.8	87.6	25.6	75.0	24.0
IR56	95.8	30.8	91.6	20.0	73.0	13.4
IR50	98.0	31.8	100	21.4	70.8	16.8
IR60	91.6	29.2	77.0	14.4	58.4	10.0
IR42	70.8	23.0	60.4	12.0	—	—
IR22	75.0	25.0	62.4	12.4	—	—
IR58	58.4	16.8	81.2	20.8	70.8	20.8
IR62	68.8	17.8	79.0	19.4	70.8	18.2
IR36	66.6	15.6	85.4	16.4	60.4	9.2
IR20	43.8	22.4	58.4	13.2	56.2	12.0
IR54	39.6	11.8	67.6	24.0	60.8	21.8
IR26	75.0	26.2	64.6	19.8	60.4	18.6

^a Mean of 2 replications. ^b Susceptible check.